

Lochaxt (Cham, Heiligkreuz, Inv.-Nr. 1910_77.1)

**Processing Report
07 July 2022**

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	192	Camera stations:	192
Flying altitude:	17.6 cm	Tie points:	110,430
Ground resolution:	0.0235 mm/pix	Projections:	398,218
Coverage area:	44.2 cm ²	Reprojection error:	1.14 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro ...	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm	No
ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro ...	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm).

ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm)

99 images

Type

Resolution

Focal Length

Pixel Size

Frame

6000 x 4000

30 mm

4 x 4 μm

	Value	Error	P1	P2
F	7500			
P1	-0.000709771	2.5e-05	1.00	-0.19
P2	0.000235774	3.3e-05		1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm).

ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm)

93 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm

	Value	Error	P1	P2
F	7500			
P1	-0.000755901	2.3e-05	1.00	-0.19
P2	-0.000163243	4e-05		1.00

Table 3. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Scale Bars

Label	Distance (m)	Error (m)
point 3_point 4	0.100001	8.84913e-07
Total		8.84913e-07

Table 4. Control scale bars.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 0.221 mm/pix
Point density: 20.5 points/mm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	192
Aligned cameras	192
Markers	2
Scale bars	1
Coordinate system	Local Coordinates (m)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	110,430 of 191,424
RMS reprojection error	0.131254 (1.13867 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.765091 (39.8653 pix)
Mean key point size	6.91696 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	3.57566
File size	13.54 MB

Depth Maps

Count	192
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	15 minutes 35 seconds
File size	585.42 MB

Model

Faces	254,679
Vertices	127,342
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	8,192 x 8,192, 4 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	15 minutes 35 seconds

Reconstruction parameters

Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Depth maps
Interpolation	Disabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	2 minutes 46 seconds
Memory usage	2.66 GB

Texturing parameters

Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Average
Texture size	8,192
Enable hole filling	No
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	32 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	220.97 MB
Blending time	1 minutes 4 seconds

Blending memory usage	2.47 GB
Date created	2022:04:25 14:23:25
Software version	1.8.2.0
File size	48.20 MB

System

Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.3 build 14331
OS	Linux 64 bit
RAM	3.83 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8265U CPU @ 1.60GHz
GPU(s)	None